

California Racing Pipelines and Their People: Collaborating with the Worldly Practicing Raceways with Resilient Goals

The capabilities of pipeline workers and inspectors have been tested, who often begin their interactions on grounds created by accidents both things and living beings. Shaping response abilities, things and living beings can be made and made human and non-human beings, at different scales of time and space. All together the pipeline workers, trigger and call forth what—and who—comes, together, knowing with and rendering capable some-dimensional niche space and its inhabitants.

Donna Haraway (2016): *Staying with the trouble*.

"... intersectionality analysis to identify vulnerable groups and inequity in biodiversity

...

Case Study 1:

Case Study 2:

Case Study 3:

Case Study 4:

Case Study 5:

Extensive Case Study:

Extensive Case Study:

Reflexivity exercise: Our privileges and our research

WHEEL OF PRIVILEGE

Source: Elsherif, Mahmoud M.; Middleton, Sara L.; Phan, Jenny Mai; Azevedo, Flavio; Iley, Bethan J.; Grose-Hodge, Magdalena; Tyler, Samantha L.; Kapp, Steven K.; Gourdon-Kanhukamwe, Amélie; Grafton-Clarke, Desiree; Yeung, Siu Kit; Shaw, John J.; Hartmann, Helena; and Dokova, Marie (2022, preprint). How Shared Values Can Guide Best Practices for Research Integrity, Social Justice, and Principled Education. DOI: [10.31222/osf.io/k7a9p](https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/k7a9p)

Exchange on starting points for
intersectional perspectives in our case
studies
Group work:
names

room green

Geraldine Brown

Ilkhom Soliev, MLU, Germany

Katherine DB (UNEP-WCMC)

Subash Ludhra

Zafar Saydaliev

Dadima
intergenerat
ional walks
(non-white)

In situ (not
in the form
of surveys,
etc.)

CGE
urban
youth

Need to build
trust with new
learning
communities

For experience and
impact (on the spot
as an exercise)

For knowledge
(could be surveys)

Be mindful
that exercises
can trigger
anxiety

inform
ourselves
(researchers,
partners),
policy, society

Exchange on starting points for intersectional perspectives in our case studies

Group work:

Ghezal, Sandra, Andreas, Torsten, György

room violet

- AM Andreas Motschiunig FUG
- G Ghezal_FiBL
- GP György Pataki (essrg)
- if Sandra Karner, IFZ, Austria
- TW Torsten Wähler (MLU) - Germany

green spaces
were designed
for privileged
people: how to
get e.g. migrant
people engaged

accessibility: in
which
neighbourhoods
are they located?
How much cares
the city about
different places?

family
traditions:
paternal family
structures =>
role of women

unconscious
choice of
meals - meal
cultures?

education;
how remote
are the people
located?

Intervention: Top-down
versus bottom-up; what
kind of societal contract
would we be able to
establish? Invited v.s. non-
invited intervention

multiple
inequalities

connecting to
people: by setting
up cooperation
with e.g. commun
centres; commun
representatives

low hanging
fruits vs.
tackling "real
pain points"

which
group(s) to
focus on?

connect with
already exist
activities; join
community; g
their place

home garden
community tries to
uphold diversity
(alternative
farmers,
homegardeners,
etc.)

farming
community: topic
is marginalised;
knowledge
disappears

market
logics are
driving the
interest

gender as
starting point -
very relevant; the
topic itself is
disadvantages

consumers
are not aware
about agro-
biodiversity

seed preservers
are almost
female; new
farmers: couples;
old farmers: for
heritage reasons

kind of
hobby -
often not
commercial

health
related
issues?

Exchange on starting points for intersectional perspectives in our case studies

Group work:
names

room blue

- AP Amalia Podlaszewska - CGE Germany
- BL Bori Lipka (ESSRG)
- HF Helene Figari (NINA)
- R Robert Home (FIBL)
- SV Simon Vaño

Privilege to do
what? How is
privilege
manifest?

The categories in the
wheel might not be
easy to use in our case
studies because some
categories are missing,
while others aren't
relevant.

e.g disabled
children in
accessing
green areas

inclusive
planning
process (?)

Urban
Youth

Migration

Labor
market

we need to know
about the
infrastructure available
to immigrant workers.
Can they participate in
the societies where
they live?

Discrimination can be very
deep, such as denying that
disabled people have the
right to visit nature.
Images of groups, and
associated prejudices and
stereotypes can be very
powerful.

Privilege vs. inclusivity
= being part of the
race, but starting at
the different distance
from the finish line Vs.
not being part of the
race

There can be a conflict of interest when
including disadvantaged groups of
people. it can happen that the conflicts
can be internal to the groups. e.g. in
participatory planning there can be
conflicts in how to digitalise. so
moderators want to accommodate
needs, but don't actually WANT the
opinions of some participants.

Privilege is a difficult
concept. Those with
relative privilege have the
ability to influence the
privilege of others. And
perhaps the duty to NOT
discriminate, which means
actively recognising the
factors of privilege.

